

Translation of the holy Margrethe

By Svend Clausen, TBC

Entry tags: Judicial Procedure, Latin Text, Catholic, Religious Group, Christianity, Text, Hagiography, Catholic Devotional Texts, Catholic text

The text is interesting as Margrethe is the only indigenous Danish woman who was both venerated as a saint and of whom written source material is also preserved. She was a noble woman personally related to the famous Danish archbishop Absalon. Details of her life are scarce, but her family relations to Absalon and thereby also to the powerful Hvide family clan seems to show that she probably originated from the island of Zealand. The text begins its story only at her death telling how, in the year 1176, she was murdered by her husband Herlog. Afterwards Herlog hung her body on a rafter to make it look like she had committed suicide by hanging thus making himself look innocent. The local priest believed the suicide to be true and therefore denied her a burial on the holy ground of the cemetery. Instead, apparently, she was buried on a field near the beach where a chapel was later erected. When lights in the sky at night over the burial site marked her innocence, it was reported to Absalon who at that time was still bishop in the local diocese of Roskilde. Even though he was skeptical, the rumours increased and he therefore had an investigation begun. He then confronted Herlog who admitted his guilt. Margrethe's relatives wanted to take revenge on Herlog, but Absalon managed to calm them down. Fronting a great crowd he then travelled to the burial site where her body was dug up, washed and carried in procession back to the town of Roskilde. The text concludes by describing how she was buried with great pomp in the Church of the Virgin Mary where many miracles later happened at her burial site. It has sometimes been mentioned that she buried in the famous Roskilde cathedral originally. However, it is known from later documents, though, that her saint's cult was attached to the still preserved monastery church of the abbey of the Cistercian nuns in Roskilde. This monastery church probably served as her original burial site in Roskilde all along. An attempt to have her papally canonized probably did not become successful, but this seems to have had little immediate effect on the popularity of her cult locally in the Roskilde diocese where her cult appears to have remained popular throughout the 13th C. and perhaps also during the later middle ages. The text was written sometime after c. 1191/1192, but most likely before March 1201.

Date Range: 1176 CE - 1201 CE

Region: Diocese of Roskilde

Region tags: Denmark

Rough map of the diocese of Roskilde during the late 12th and the 13th C., where Margrethe was venerated here centering on the island of Zealand.

Status of Readership:

✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

— Source 1: M. Cl. Gertz: *Vitae Sanctorum Danorum*, Selskabet for Udgivelse af Kilder til dansk Historie, København, 1908-1912

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: https://wiki.app.uib.no/medieval/index.php?title=Sancta_Margareta
- Source 1 Description: background information in English

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

Specify type of paper

– Specify: Paper (nowadays), parchment (originally)

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: Original manuscript is not preserved

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

Specify

– Specify: In the 12th and 13th C. it was most likely stored in Roskilde somewhere it was also written

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– Field doesn't know

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– Field doesn't know

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Yes

↳ Are the authors/copyists/engravers paid by the polity?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is not known, but it might have been the case to some extent due to that the author must have been a clerk in Roskilde likely somehow officially connected to either the diocesan church or the cistercian nunnery in the town - most likely probably the former option of the two.

↳ Does the polity provide financial support to religious infrastructure involved with textual production?

– Yes

Notes: Not known for sure, but probably somehow

↳ Are the leaders of the polity and the religion the same figure?

– No

Notes: Although as for bishop of diocese of Roskilde the answer is yes to some extent.

↳ Are political officials involved in the support of textual production?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Not known, but perhaps they were in the sense that a clerk from the diocese of Roskilde might have been the author

↳ Are political officials and religious officials otherwise overlapping institutional networks?

– Yes

↳ Does the polity enforce religious observance according to text or texts?

– Yes

Notes: There seems to have been an attempt to give her cult at least somewhat of a semi-official status in the diocese during the 11th and 12th C., although it never quite happened to the full extent.

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Notes: Although as for the local saint's cult of Margrethe it must have been considered the official version.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Notes: latin

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Field doesn't know

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Notes: Although the answer could be yes e.g. in the sense that a chapel was erected at her original burial site.

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: original manuscript is lost

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: hagiography

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: None of the above

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Notes: Although the answer is yes in the sense that the text involved that she was venerated at a specific date

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs?

– Yes

↳ In cemetery?

– No

Notes: The answer is yes in the sense that it is mentioned that she was initially denied a burial in the cemetery.

– No

Notes: The answer is yes in the sense that it is mentioned that she was initially denied a burial in the cemetery.

↳ Family tomb-crypt?

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities)?

– No

↳ Other formal burial type?

– Yes

Notes: A translatio

↳ Other intensive funerary ritual

– Specify: A procession

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– Yes

Notes: For her veneration as a saint

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s)?

– No

↳ For the worship of a deified human?

– No

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero?

– No

↳ For the veneration of a deceased person(s)?

– No

↳ For the veneration of a deified human?

– No

↳ For the veneration of a deceased hero?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: none of the above

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

Notes: Herlog's acts represent the opposite of this, of course

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– No

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– No

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– No

↳ Generosity/charity

– No

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– No

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

Notes: Righteousness is restored when the light reveal her sanctity, the murder is solved and her body is translated

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– No

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– No

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– No

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– No

↳ Cooperation

– No

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– No

↳ Moderation/frugality

– No

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– No

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– No

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– No

↳ Strength (physical)

– No

- ↳ Power/status/nobility
 - No
- ↳ Humility/modesty
 - No
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
 - No
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
 - No
- ↳ Optimism/hope
 - No
- ↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
 - No
- ↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
 - No
- ↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
 - No
- ↳ Wisdom/understanding
 - No
- ↳ Discernment/intelligence
 - No
- ↳ Beauty/attractiveness
 - No
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness
 - No

↳ Other important virtues

– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Notes: It is not known with certainty to which institution the author was connected

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: None of the above

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Translation of the holy Margrethe, Olrik, Hans , trans.. Danske Helgeners Levned, Vol. II. Translated by Hans Olrik. Copenhagen: Selskabet til Historiske Kildeskrifters Oversættelse, 1894.

Reference: Translation of the holy Margrethe, Damsholt, Nanna. Kvindebilledet I Dansk Højmiddelalder. København: Borgen, 1985.

Reference: Translation of the holy Margrethe, Weibull, Lauritz . "En Samtida Berättelse Från Clairvaux Om Ärkebiskop Eskil Av Lund". Scandia IV (1931): 270–90.

Reference: Translation of the holy Margrethe, Søgaard, Helge . "Overleveringen Om Den Hellige Margrete Af Roskilde". Historie XV (1983): 476–83.